

Engaging stakeholders in the CDR science-policy challenge

Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) methods are increasingly being explored as a puzzle piece for reaching net zero greenhouse gas emissions¹. At the same time, existing uncertainties regarding the potential of CDR methods – and associated costs and risks – call for cautious and deliberative governance². There is a growing recognition, particularly in climate research, of the **importance of transdisciplinary collaboration and the integration of external actors** in research, implementation and regulation of CDR.

This is **especially amplified by two features inherent to CDR**: Firstly, the **primary (and often singular) value of CDR** is its **contribution to the public good of climate change mitigation** (i.e., tons of CO₂ removed from and safely stored outside the atmosphere). At the same time, it aggravates **competition for limited resources** such as land, water, renewable energy and biomass. Secondly, the diverse CDR methods touch **upon a large variety of pivotal economic sectors and ecosystems** – requiring infrastructure investments,

transformation, and oftentimes trade-offs in sectors such as energy, waste, forestry and agriculture. This highlights the importance of scrutinizing these technologies for their mitigation potential, associated risks, and co-benefits, as well as addressing concerns that they may divert attention from emissions reduction priorities. As such, the urgency of implementing effective climate change mitigation measures, along with concerns surrounding these measures, puts a science-policy challenge on embedding CDR in the climate policy landscape³.

Stakeholder engagement is a key ingredient for negotiating concerns about CDR methods and opening a path towards CDR-policies and implementation projects that are efficient, ethical and feasible⁴. Within the CDRterra research program, researchers engaged with stakeholders from various geographical regions and sectors on a range of CDR options. The program also addressed policymaking and societal impacts related to specific technologies, as well as the role of CDR in net zero strategies.

Main takeaways

- **In public tenders, establish requirements for a high level of involvement and allocate sufficient resources for stakeholder engagement.**
- **Ensure balanced stakeholder representation and proactively balance particular interests and biases in the engagement process. Not all affected groups and organizations have the same resources, capacities and urgency to participate and have their voice heard.**
- **Design stakeholder engagement processes for mutual learning and incorporate flexibility to adapt policies and project plans based on these learnings. Whenever resources are allocated to CDR, there is a realistic risk of rebound effects and delay of emission reduction efforts.**

In this policy brief we share recommendations for stakeholder engagement both in the research and in the development and implementation of CDR, as well as CDR-related policy making. The recommendations are based on learnings from active stakeholder engagement in Germany and other European countries⁵. More explanations on the key points and recommendations are presented in the following:

The earlier the better: Proactively involving societal stakeholders early in the process of research, development, piloting, regulation, and funding of CDR methods clears the path to an effective, broadly supported, fair and sustainable scale-up of CDR towards net zero emissions.

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Politics and public administration play a pivotal role in preventing CDR-developments from running into dead ends and polarized debates around, e.g., infrastructure projects and investments. A key factor for success is strengthening the role of stakeholder engagement in CDR-related research and implementation processes, as well as policy design, in the following manner:

- Funding bodies and awarding institutions in the field of CDR research should demand stakeholder engagement with a high level of involvement as central components of any project. This presupposes that **sufficient resources are allocated within public tenders for stakeholder engagement** and the synthesis and transfer of results at the science-society and science-policy interfaces.

- **Engaging with relevant actors with diverse, representative perspectives** should be an integral part of every CDR-related research and implementation project, shaping and informing the process through the entire project cycle. Stakeholder engagement should not be seen as an end-of-pipe knowledge transfer alone.

- When mandating or leading stakeholder engagements, it is key to **ensure the separation of research and particular interests**.

- **A focus on region-specific, suitable CDR methods** increases the relevance for regional and local stakeholders and residents, making the topics more tangible.

- A trusted relationship with stakeholders and a real-world impact of the engagements depends on mutual learning and especially **openness to adapt project plans and policy drafts** based on these learnings.

At the current early stage of implementation and public debate around CDR, not all actors are willing or able to allocate the same amount of resources to forming an opinion on the complex matter and participate proactively in engagement processes. This leads to a bias: Who gets heard and wields influence in the process?

While the emerging CDR industry shows a high presence in stakeholder engagement activities, other key stakeholder groups such as environmental NGOs or farmers, may have trouble allocating their resources to an unpaid engagement process on a topic that is just one among many on their agendas and everyday concerns.

As stakeholder engagement becomes increasingly central to research in the field of CDR, it is up to policymakers and decision-makers to support well-balanced deliberative approaches and advance them when it comes to just and effective financing, regulation and implementation of CDR.

Rebound effects and deterrence of emission reduction can manifest whenever resources are allocated to CDR. This puts net-mitigation efforts at risk. Stakeholder engagements can play a key role in reducing this risk and negotiating systemic impacts of CDR-related policy- and decision-making.

Mitigation deterrence occurs when certain climate actions give a false sense of progress. This can delay and even prevent more effective and more efficient solutions⁶. For example, relying on large-scale CDR to be realized in an uncertain future may reduce efforts to address the root causes of greenhouse gas emissions, divert resources from reduction measures and lessen the urgency of climate policy.

A discourse with representative stakeholders and experts can help identify where problems might arise due to shifts in climate policy discourse, but also mis-incentives or competition over resources. Such considerations are advisable for each concrete CDR implementation and policy decision. Like this, the usually abstract topic of mitigation deterrence becomes tangible. This helps navigate politicized discourses and identify specific ways to improve policy design and to avoid greenwashing, as well as lock-in and rebound effects. Based on stakeholder deliberation, safeguards to minimize the risk of mitigation deterrence can be implemented. This involves adaptive policy planning, acknowledging the remaining uncertainties and risks.

CDR is a growing field that is receiving increasing attention from a variety of stakeholders across science, economy, politics, NGOs, etc. As effective climate mitigation under time pressure is needed, it is more important than ever to actively consider all relevant perspectives.

CONCLUSION

Co-creative, deliberative stakeholder engagement is crucial to ensure that the development of CDR at a climate-relevant scale comes with a holistic aspiration, enabling a development and deployment of value-chains that are both effective in contributing to net zero pathways and adhere to high societal standards of legitimacy, fairness, and social, environmental, and economic sustainability. In this way, effective stakeholder engagement can also help mitigate hardened opposition to policies and CDR infrastructure projects, but also perverse incentives and rebound effects such as mitigation deterrence.

IN A NUTSHELL:

- Stakeholder involvement should be integrated into every stage of CDR research and policymaking to ensure diverse perspectives shape the process. Sufficient resources must be allocated to do so.
- Researchers, policymakers, and implementation project managers must ensure balanced and representative participation, especially when key stakeholders face challenges in allocating resources for these discussions.
- Stakeholder engagement processes should be designed for mutual learning and incorporate flexibility to adapt policies and project plans based on these learnings. At the same time, particular interests and biases in the engagement process should be navigated with care.
- Mitigation deterrence occurs when certain climate actions give a false sense of progress, resulting in a delay of net emission reduction. Policymakers should be attuned to any sign of mitigation deterrence occurring on the level of competition for funding and resources for CDR vs. decarbonization, in addition to challenges to ambition in climate policies and net zero strategies of companies and governmental actors.

About CDR-PoEt (2021 - 2025)

Carbon Dioxide Removals – Policies and Ethics (CDR-PoEt) examines the ethical and equity implications of policy instruments for CDR, based on interdisciplinary research and stakeholder deliberations. The project specifically evaluates the feasibility (“what can we do from an economic, socio-cultural, and institutional perspective?”) and the desirability (“what do we want to do?”) of CDR policies and methods in their specific contexts, providing a foundation for developing policy recommendations at local, national and international levels.

 https://twitter.com/CDR_PoEt
 <https://cdrterra.de/en/consortia/cdr-poet>
 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/carbon-dioxide-removal-policies-and-ethics-cdr-poet/>

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